

THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATIVE LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract. *In this methodological recommendation, it is thought that the use of additional exercises in mother tongue lessons in elementary grades increases the effectiveness of the lesson, plays a great role in gaining children's interest in the lesson.*

Keywords: *native language, class, teaching, primary class, generation-ancestors, spirituality, land, reading techniques, free thinking, purpose.*

In elementary grades, it is important for students to perform thematic exercises in strengthening a new topic. Because when a rule and a thematic grammatical concept fail to perform thematic exercises after being taught to students, it becomes difficult for students to learn and Master The taught rules and grammatical concepts perfectly.

To check the benefits of doing additional exercises on the topic in elementary grades, to analyze the experience after passing the topic in the classroom, we performed two additional exercises on the topic in order to strengthen it. The topic was firmly mastered by readers. We explained the grammatical concepts on the topic to our supervised class through some examples, did the exercise given in the textbook, but did not perform additional exercises on the topic. As a result, it has been a little difficult for us to explain the thematic rule to readers. The process of giving grammatical concepts required spending some time.

When we asked questions to determine if the students had mastered the subject, the answers to the questions did not give the result we expected. We have witnessed that 40% of readers have mastered the topic. So, when mastering a new topic and strengthening by readers, of course, additional exercises on the topic should be performed.

A person's thinking, scientific potential, ability are considered as socially important qualities. The fact that in the future our homeland will be prosperous and free, free and prosperous, economically energetic largely depends on the talent, talent, deep thinking, knowledgeable and spiritual of today's youth. In the maturation of the younger generation, the importance of mother tongue education is great, and the mother tongue is important not only in mastering the same subjects, but also in the formation of communication in society, in the presence of a person in society as a whole, in their initiation into interaction. Teaching consists of creating new, efficient, improved methods and technologies, testing it in experience and generating a more perfected direction in the process of perfect application, an improved textbook, modern methods and technologies influence the correct course of education. Today, the main thing about the tasks that the native language classes set for young people is to deliver their thoughts logically consistently, impressively, with all the possibilities embodied.

In the implementation of pedagogical technology, more precisely, modern pedagogical technology in education, on the one hand, most students are looking for a certain degree after serious attention, and on the other hand, as a result of the application of most problems in training, faced with various non-traditional methods, knowledge is fully given, which is obliged to be

occupied by students who have When the teacher pays attention to the following aspects in the introduction of modern pedagogical technology in the educational process, the goal is achieved: a person-the available opportunities in the student-stability of attention, being able to do mental work, taking into account the level of activity, speech, competence in creative search: the formation of a certain algorithm in the educational process (continuity of: in the process of implementing the project, it is necessary to control to what extent the educational goals of the lesson are being realized: language opportunities in the lesson to go through various additional tools, technical types, music, fairy tales, riddles, Proverbs, poems, rebus, etc.

The qualifications of teachers of the school's native language in the courses of organizing the improvement on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies, it will be necessary to reduce the audience to the state of the student by introducing themselves into the process and guiding them to find a solution to the problem before recommending the audience to achieve educational efficiency, enrich the content of Only then does the teacher understand the student even more, able to feel his feelings.

The present lesson is that the student, the listener, and the teacher should not remain speakers. Perhaps the teacher should become a director who will monitor the lesson and regulate it. The teacher should organize the lesson in such a way that all the student will have an independent opinion on this topic, be able to say his opinion, be able to correct it based on the answers of his fellow students and the teacher. Depending on the character nature of the lesson, the lesson should be achieved in an interactive way. The use of tests and handouts in classes also gives a good result. When instilling language education in students, it is necessary to also take into account their age and level of knowledge. Because if a 2nd grader is given a 4th grade volume of knowledge the student cannot digest it, nor can he master it. Rather limited to giving a Grade 4 student knowledge in grades 1-2, this is also annoying for the student. As a result, students have an obsession with learning the language, with interest fading rather than developing.

A modern teacher should be a “director”, not an “actor”, in the course of the lesson. It is necessary to organize a lesson for its students to view science with creativity, to form the characteristics of their research in them, as well as using new pedagogical technologies. And for this, it is advisable for the teacher to know new educational methods and norms, to use them effectively in the course of the lesson.

Interactive methods Why do we need them? Interactive methods presuppose the goal of achieving high results in a short time, without excessive mental and physical exertion. An interactive method is a method that activates learners and encourages independent thinking, and is the educational one at the heart of the educational process. Interactive methods and methods: “Keys-stadi”, “Blist-request”, “modeling”, “Sinkwein”, “BBB”, “Venn diagram”, “t table”, “cluster”, “Balik scaleti”, “mental attack”, “Zinama - zina”, “host”, etc. "Muzyorar" is a type of active activity of a certain kind, which is designed to prevent the indifference of students in the classroom in which the lesson is held, to avoid the fatigue generated during the course of the lesson and the mental pressure on students. So they can be used to prevent class-induced “freezing” and to melt and crack if such “freezing” has formed. Many teachers use” musicians ” only in the initial stage of education, but it can also be used with similar success during the lesson, when communication with students or between students becomes difficult for certain reasons. Some of the student-specific “musiyarar ” are intended for the reader or students to get to know each other,

and include individuals in groups asking each other questions to gain mutual information about their study or working conditions, meditating on what they like.

To what extent is the mother tongue teacher currently using these new educational methods and techniques? The informatization of society requires continuous innovation in the educational system. Today, any style can immediately wear out and be enriched with new techniques. What factors does it depend on to achieve the desired results in the lesson? Research has been done on the application of innovation in education by many researchers in different countries of the world.

In conclusion, the use of modern technologies that reflect the directions of modern education within themselves increases the effectiveness of native language lessons. Modern technologies - activities carried out using game methods, affecting the personal behavior of students, as an external observer, a characterizing force, help children to reveal the content of professional labor in combination with mastering the science of elementary educational methodology. Until this time, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge. Such a method would quench independent thinking, creative search, initiative in students. Nowadays, the interest, attention to raising the effectiveness of education, using interactive methods (innovative pedagogical and information technologies) in the educational process, is gaining momentum day by day. The training in which modern technologies are applied is aimed at students looking for the knowledge they are acquiring, independently studying and analyzing it, and even drawing conclusions themselves. In this process, the teacher creates conditions for the development, formation, knowledge and upbringing of the individual and the team, and, among other things, acts as a steward, a guide. In such a learning process, the student becomes the main figure.

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